

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' RHETORICAL COMPETENCE

M. Abatova

basic doctoral student

Ajiniyaz Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

Introduction. In recent years, various reforms have been implemented in our country to improve the quality of higher education, enhance students' professional-pedagogical training, optimize the teaching and educational process, increase the effectiveness of instruction, clearly define objectives at each stage of education, and develop mechanisms for mastering knowledge as fully as possible. Particularly in higher education, special attention is being given to organizing and assessing teaching based on international European standards, including the use of technologies aimed at developing students' rhetorical competence, especially in foreign language instruction.

In today's modern educational system, developing students rhetorical competence is considered a crucial task.

Rhetorical skills- refer to the ability to express ideas clearly, logically, and persuasively, to speak confidently in public, and to engage in communication with self-assurance. These skills help students not only during the learning process but also in their professional careers and personal lives. This article presents a methodology developed for enhancing students' rhetorical competence.

Methods. Researcher D.Seytkasimov examined the communicative competencies that are essential to the professional competence of philology students (Karakalpak language and literature). This research is aimed at developing the professional communication skills of students studying in the field of Karakalpak language and literature, and the classification of communicative competencies ensures a clear and systematic approach in the educational process. The classification methodology presented in the study serves as an important tool for improving students' speech culture, logical thinking, and effective communication abilities.

Researcher M.M.Musurmonkulova's work is based on creative approaches aimed at developing students' oratory and independent thinking skills in literature teaching. In her research, she developed methods to improve students' speech culture through the use of problem-based lectures, case studies, and didactic materials. In our opinion, the creative approach developed through the use of problem-based lectures, case studies, and didactic materials is considered effective in improving students' speech culture, serves to enhance the quality of education, and can be widely applied in the field of philology.

Researcher O.Turakulova focused on independent thinking and speech culture to develop students' oratory skills in literature lessons. In her methodology, she applied specific situation analysis (case study) and problem-based teaching methods to increase students' communication activity. These methods contributed to the development of students' skills in structuring speech logically and expressing themselves effectively. These scholars used various methodologies to develop oratory competence, with their main approaches based on interactive, problem-based teaching, psychological, and linguistic methods. Their research has served to improve students'

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speech culture, independent thinking, and effective communication skills. It is recommended that further studies be conducted in the future to apply these methodologies in other subjects and educational levels.

During our research process, problems were studied while conducting investigations on improving the oratory competence of philology students in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Navoi region. In the study, the current state of students' oratory competence was examined through questionnaire surveys. Table

Are you ready to talk about honesty on television?	QSU		NSPI		Navoiy SPU	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
	4	5	4	5	4	5
	3,0	7,0	9,3	0,7	6,6	3,4

The survey results were "unsatisfactory" by students of KSU (57.0%), "unsatisfactory" by students of NSPI (50.7%), and "unsatisfactory" by students of Navoi SPI (53.4%). If we look at the indicated answers, the majority of students showed that they are in favor of teaching the subject of public speaking.

As we have seen, students learned that it is necessary to include the subjects "Oratory," "Pedagogical Mastery," "Pedagogical Conflictology" in the curriculum. For this purpose, we studied the following methods for developing the oratory skills of methodology students. (Fig. 1)

To assess students' rhetorical competence, the following methods were used to form a hypothesis (Table 2).

Assessment of students' oratory competence	
Speech quality assessment	Experts will evaluate student presentations on a 5-point scale (accuracy, effectiveness, structure, and non-verbal elements).
Survey	A questionnaire is conducted to determine the level of students' self-confidence and fear associated with public speaking.
Observation	Communicative activity of students is observed during the classes.

According to the research results, the oratory competence of students in the experimental group increased significantly. The full results are as follows:

Speech quality: The presentations of students in the experimental group were assessed on an average of 4.2 points (on a 5-point scale), while in the control group this indicator is 3.1 points.

Self-confidence: According to the survey results, the level of fear of public speaking decreased in 85% of students in the experimental group, while in the control group this indicator was 40%.

Nonverbal elements: Students in the experimental group showed 30% good results in nonverbal communication skills (gestures and intonation).

Discussion: The research results show that the specially developed methodology has high effectiveness in the development of students' oratory competence. Interactive classes and psychological trainings played an important role in increasing students' self-confidence and communication skills.

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Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена методике, направленной на развитие ораторской компетенции студентов. Статья включает в себя интерактивные занятия, психологические тренинги, невербальное общение и методы логического мышления. В статье приводятся практические рекомендации по развитию ораторских навыков в учебном процессе.

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Ключевые слова: Ораторская компетенция, студенты, методика обучения, публичные выступления, интерактивные занятия, психологическая подготовка, невербальное общение, образование.

Abstract: This article is dedicated to the methodology aimed at developing students' oratory competence. The article contains interactive lessons, psychological trainings, nonverbal communication, and methods of logical thinking. The article provides practical recommendations for developing oratory skills in the learning process.

Keywords: Oratory competence, students, educational methodology, public speaking, interactive exercises, psychological preparation, nonverbal communication, education.